

The Analysis of “The Source of Pleasure and the Cloth of Blessings”

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Abstract: In the article the gastronomic features of the people of Bukhara of XIX century, such as the thinker Rakhmatullo Vozekh, stated in the treatise “The Source of Pleasure and the Cloth of Blessings” are considered.

Key words: recipes, cookery, gastronomic feature, versions of flat cakes, plov, jam.

Introduction

In consciousness at many orientalists and experts’ poetry Bukhara is associated with those epithets which known travelers, historians, scientists and researchers deservedly awarded it. Bukhara is known for its museums and architectural monuments, products of national masters of crafts, folklores which reflect a rich historical and architectural heritage, national traditions, and especially traditional culinary art. The gastronomy of Central Asia is a way of acquaintance with the culture, traditions and features of local people and nations. Recently the gastronomy and cookery even more often have become the basic motive of a choice of a travel direction. The delicatessen is a complex concept which goes back to antique times.

The main part. An ancient Greek poet Arhestrat wrote a book on a delicatessen with the title which is literally translated “Laws for a Stomach”. The people of Central Asia have also left the indelible contribution in the world heritage of cookery. A well-known poet, scientist and thinker of XIX century lived in Bukharian emirate Kori Rakhmatullo Vozekh is considered as one of such researchers of national gastronomic culture.

Kori Rakhmatullo Vozekh (1817-1894) – an Uzbek educator, writer, he was the adviser of Bukharian emir Muzaffar. Vozekh knew history, medicine, mathematics, Islamic jurisprudence, astronomy and other sciences well. He wrote poems in the Uzbek, Tadjik and Arabian languages. He left a big literary heritage, approximately to 25 compositions of various genres.

Among them the anthology written in 1871 “Tuhfat al-ahbab fitazkirat al-ashab” (The Gift to favorites with the biography of friends), it includes the data of Bukharian poets and scientists of the 18th-19th centuries, the travel book “Savanikh al-masalik va farasikh al-mamalik” (Incidents on the Ways and

Farsahi States, 1887); the gastronomic treatise “Koni lazzat va khoni nemat” (The Source of Pleasure and the Cloth of Blessings, 1880) which describes Middle Asian, Arabian, Iranian and Indian cuisine extended in Bukharian Emirate; a satiric work about superstitions and prejudices “Akoid-un-niso” (Women’s Belief, 1883) are allocated. Besides Vozekh is the author of verses and gazelles [1].

As we mentioned earlier, the ethnic cuisine and culinary heritage of people is the way of acquaintance with culture and mentality of local population of Uzbekistan. Kori Rakhmatullo Vozekh Bukharian his culinary work “Koni lazzat va khoni nemat” (The Source of Pleasure and the Cloth of Blessings) describes a life and cookery of local residents of Bukhara. His treatise written in 1880, the author devoted to Muzaffar, Bukharian emir. 227 recipes of dishes, varieties of Plov, kinds of halvah, jam and flat cakes are presented in this book. The recipes of not only Central Asian kitchen, but also dishes of the Hindus and Iranians lived in Bukhara are described. Some recipes are supplied with manufacturing techniques. The treatise consists of a preface, two basic parts and a final chapter. 18 kinds of bread are described in the book, and then the description of 109 kinds of dishes is given [3]. The first part consists of 22 units, and the second part comprises 20 units in which 169 kinds of halvah are given. Vozekh describes in detail the principle of preparation and useful medical properties of dishes in the treatise. The author systematized and classified dishes under names of the Arabian alphabet. For example, “Bobi alif” (The Unit of Alif), “Bobi dol” (The Unit of Dol), “Bobi sin” (The Unit of Sin) etc [2].

In the first part of the book the names of the dishes are given: ibrokhimia, oshi anbarboris, oshi ugro, olu bolu palav, oshi hordes, oshi rishta, anor palav, bokila palav, barro, bari, barii kashmiri, buroni jazar, isfanoj, buroni bodinjon, buroni khiyor, buroni morchuba, bovardi, bugro, bugroi anor, bugroi khorazmi, yakhni palav, lukma palav, shibet palav, palavi soda, palavi zard, palavi khanoni, a burak, bakhat, jamol palav, chuk palav, javoziba, jazaria, chalov, jushira, ranginak, sumokia, uja, asida and others [2].

In the book the author results the kinds of flat cakes, halvahs and jam which were well-known among the population of Bukhara, Samarkand, Kokand and other places of Uzbekistan, such as: noni shirmol, noni kumoch, noni varaki, noni nakhudi, noni sagak, noni tafton, halvoi tar, halvoi ordi, halvoi kunjut, halvoi lavzi, halvoi shakar khamir, halvoi angur, halvoi pista, halvoi sobuni, halvoi maghzi, murabboi olucha, murabboi pusti tarbuz, murabboi sabzi, murabboi bihi, murabboi tut, murabboi rayhon, murabboi amrud and others.

Many recipes are unusual under recipes of preparation and are peculiar to the people of Central Asia, and some of them even are lost. Sweets were prepared with additives from nuts, pistachios, kunjut and almonds. And jams were prepared from a water-melon, carrots, pears, petals of roses, a cherry, a quince, mulberry fruits and others fruit.

In his book the author describes useful properties of murabboi olucha, i.e., jam from a cherry so: “... galabia safro binshonad va tashnagi ro sokin gardonad. Bigirand oluchai sultoni har qadar ki khokhand va dar degi sangi kunand va du-se jush doda furud girand, digar bora bo asal yo kand yo shaker tabkh namoyand” (diminishes bile and calms thirst).

It is necessary to take a king cherry, how much you want and put in a stone copper; boil it twice or three times, then add honey or sugar, and bring to thicken [2].

Conclusion. If to sum up, the importance of the treatise “Koni lazzat khoni nemat” (The Source of Pleasure and the Cloth of Blessings) is that it opens medical properties of dishes and has medical

value.

It is necessary to consider, that today gastronomy is not only a way of selection of products and cooking, it is also a complex of economic, social, religious and cultural features of countries and nations. The delicatessen of the concrete country reflects not only natural value as the geography, landscape, climate, but also local culture, such as traditions and customs, and also contains echoes of ancient ceremonies, national medicine, transfers features which are peculiar family way of the local people.

References

1. Литературный энциклопедический словарь. – М.: Советская энциклопедия. Под редакцией В.М. Кожевникова, П. А. Николаева. 1987, Р. 44. “Экономика и социум” №1(56) 2019 www.iupr.ru 59
2. Неъматзода Т. «Кони лаззат ва хони неъмат»-и Возеҳ. -Dushanbe, 1967, Р. 111-120.
3. Vozekh “Koni lazzat va xoni ne’mat” (Источник наслаждения и скатерть благ) Bukharian Museum of Art, department of manuscripts, manuscript 23056/11, 1298/1880 y.
1. Mavlanova Ugiloy Khamdamovna, Ruzieva Dilfuza Salimboevna, Babaeva Vasila Toshpulatovna. Irony in dramatic works//International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation. – 2020. – Т. 24. – №. 3.
2. Mavlonova U. K., Maxmurovna M. K. THE INTRODUCTION OF IRONY IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LITERATURE //International Engineering Journal for Research & Development. – 2020. – Т. 5. – №. 3. – С. 4-4.
3. Ugiloy Khamdamovna Mavlonova, Dilfuza Salimboyevna Ruziyeva. THE USE OF IRONY IN LITERATURE // International Scientific Journal Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – Issue 04, Volume 84. SOI: 1.1/TAS DOI: 10.15863/TAS
4. Mavlonova Ugiloy Khamdamovna 2020. Similarities and differences between types of comic. *International Journal on Integrated Education*. 3, 9 (Sep. 2020), 105-107. DOI:https://doi.org/10.31149/ijie.v3i9.596.
5. Mavlonova U.K., Makhmurova M.Kh., Kodirov T.D. DESCRIPTION OF ART MEDIA IN LITERATURE // LXIV International Correspondence Scientific and Practical Conference “EUROPEAN RESEARCH: INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY» June 5-9, 2020. London, United Kingdom
6. Sharipova D.Sh , Mavlonova U.Kh., Ibatova N.I. BEHAVIORAL LANGUAGE ETIQUETTE IN UZBEK PROVERBS AND SAYINGS // ВЕСТНИК НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ № 11(89). Часть 3. 2020. P: 51-53
7. Mavlonova U Kh, RA Akhmedova. ANALYSIS OF SITUATIONAL IRONY IN EXAMPLES FROM GENERAL CASES. ЖУРНАЛ «ACADEMY» © ИЗДАТЕЛЬСТВО «ПРОБЛЕМЫ НАУКИ». Том 62, номер 11, ст. 24-26.
8. U.K. Mavlonova, R.A. Achilova. [THE PROBLEM OF TRANSLATION OF REALIA \(AMERICANISMS\)](#). Dostijeniya nauki i obrazovaniya, 5/59, 2020.
9. Mavlonova Ugiloy Khamdamovna, “IRONY IN FITRAT’S DRAMAS”, *IEJRD - International Multidisciplinary Journal*, vol. 5, no. CONGRESS, p. 3, Nov. 2020.

10. Mavlonova Ugiloy Khamdamovna, Makhmurova Mavjuda Khalimovna. [ANALYSIS OF SITUATIONAL IRONY IN LITERATURE](#). ЖУРНАЛ «ACADEMY» © ИЗДАТЕЛЬСТВО «ПРОБЛЕМЫ НАУКИ». Том 62, номер 11, ст. 26-27.
11. Mavlonova Ugiloy Khamdamovna. (2021). IRONY IN LYRICS. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(4), 77-81. Retrieved from <https://scholarzest.com/index.php/ejrds/article/view/609>
12. У.Х. Мавлянова. [КИНОЯНИНГ ОҒЗАКИ, ВАЗИЯТЛИ ВА ДРАМАТИК КЎРИНИШЛАРДА ҚЎЛЛАНИЛИШ АҲАМИЯТИ](#) - МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА, 2021.
13. О. Mavlonova. [Kinoya yoxud istehzo turlari](#). ВЕСТНИК НУУз/ ЎзМУ хабарлари. 1 (1), 2021, 216-218-b.
14. M.U. KHAMDAMOVNA. [TYPES OF IRONY AND ITS USAGE IN THE CONTEXT](#). SCIENTIFIC REPORTS OF BUKHARA STATE UNIVERSITY/ BUXORO DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI ILMIY AXBOROTI. 2/78, 2020, 208-213. УДК: 616.89-008.444.5
15. Mavlonova Ugiloy Khamdamovna. THE ROLE OF IRONY IN UZBEK LITERATURE. SCIENTIFIC REPORTS OF BUKHARA STATE UNIVERSITY. 2021/3(85), P. 50-59
16. Khamdamovna, M.U. 2021. Aesthetic and Psychological Features of Irony. *International Journal on Integrated Education*. 4, 10 (Oct. 2021), 184-187. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.31149/ijie.v4i10.2318>.
17. Khamdamovna, M. U. (2021). The use of Irony in Uzbek Poems as a Speech Decoration. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF LITERATURE, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE*, 2(11), 17-20. <https://doi.org/10.47494/cajpc.v2i11.242>
18. Khamdamovna, M. U. . (2021). Irony and Sarcasm in English Humour. *“ONLINE - CONFERENCES" PLATFORM*, 78–82. Retrieved from <http://papers.online-conferences.com/index.php/titfl/article/view/597>
19. Mavlonova, U. (2021). ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИРОНИИ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (*buxdu.Uz*), 7(7), извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/3937
20. Mavlonova, U. (2022). ADABIY VOSITA: KINOYA VA ISTEHZO O’RTASIDAGI FARQ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (*buxdu.Uz*), 8(8). извлечено от http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/4167
21. Khamdamovna M. U., Saidakhmedovna U. D., Izatilloevna K. D. Text Forming Features of Irony in American Prose //Journal of Positive School Psychology. – 2022. – С. 9691–9697-9691–9697.
22. MU Khamdamovna. [Irony as a Topical Form of Comic](#). *International Journal on Integrated Education*. Volume 5, Issue 6, Jun 2022. P. 4-7. e-ISSN : 26203502 p-ISSN : 26153785
23. Khamdamovna, M.U. 2022. Irony Expressed by Adjectives and Verbs in English Literature. *International Journal on Integrated Education*. 5, 12 (Dec. 2022), 281-283.
24. Mavlonova, Ugiloy Khamdamovna and Saakyan, Roza Yuryevna (2023) *Characteristics of Irony and its Expression as a Component Part of Author Modality*. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 6 (4). pp. 110-114. ISSN 2620-3502
25. Mavlonova, Ugiloy Khamdamovna and Ergasheva, Fotima Rasuljonovna (2023) *Irony in World Dramas*. <https://journals.researchparks.org/index.php/IJIE/article/view/4244>, 6 (4). pp. 87-93. ISSN 2620 – 3502

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26. Mavlonova, Ugiloy Khamdamovna (2023) *Factors of Formation and Study Principles of Irony*. International Journal on Integrated Education, 6 (4). pp. 105-109. ISSN 2620-3502
 27. The Rules Of Politeness And National Features Of Etiquette In Different Countries. (2024). *Boletin De Literatura Oral - The Literary Journal*, 10(1), 3910-3918. <http://www.boletindeliteraturaoral.com/index.php/bdlo/article/view/762>